

DEVELOPING STUDENTS' TECHNICAL CREATIVITY THROUGH TEACHING THE "MAGNETIC FIELD" TOPIC USING PEDAGOGICAL SOFTWARE TOOLS

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Abstract. *This article presents the scientific and methodological foundations of using modern pedagogical and digital technologies for teaching physics in general secondary schools, particularly the "Magnetic Field" unit. The study places special emphasis on ensuring interdisciplinary integration, harmonizing students' theoretical knowledge with practical activities, and developing their algorithmic, critical, and creative thinking skills. The article analyzes the types of pedagogical software tools, their didactic capabilities, and their role in the educational process, substantiating the advantages of modeling, demonstration, training, and assessment programs. In addition, a safe instructional demonstration project titled "Captive Solenoid Demo" is proposed for studying electromagnetic induction and magnetic field phenomena. The operating principle of the device, its technical parameters, and safety requirements are described in detail. Through this project, the processes of converting electrical energy into magnetic and mechanical energy are demonstrated in a visual and comprehensible manner. The research results are significant in that they enhance students' interest in physics, encourage the development of innovative ideas, and support the acquisition of basic programming elements.*

Keywords: *physics teaching methodology, magnetic field, pedagogical software tools, interdisciplinary integration, electromagnetic induction, digital education, instructional demonstration experiment, innovative approach.*

Introduction

At the global level, considerable attention is being devoted to improving modern forms and methods of teaching natural sciences, including physics, through scientific achievements and their practical application. In this regard, there is a growing need to develop a methodological system based on modern teaching methods and tools that correspond to the content of education, aimed at developing students' interdisciplinary knowledge. This includes defining the pedagogical conditions for implementing such a system, improving the content of educational materials, and developing interactive technologies and software to facilitate their effective assimilation. Such an approach is particularly relevant, as it contributes to improving the quality of students' subject knowledge and enables the development of scientific and methodological support for the discipline.

In the general secondary education system of our country, significant attention is also paid to the development of modern didactic support for school subjects. As a result, in physics teaching-alongside other disciplines-the possibilities of instruction based on information technologies are

expanding. This makes it possible to take into account the specific characteristics of physics as a subject, simplify the teaching of complex topics through modern experimental approaches, and comprehensively demonstrate all aspects of interdisciplinary integration.

In particular, teaching the “Magnetic Field” unit [1] in physics plays a crucial role not only in shaping students’ scientific worldview within the information environment, but also in developing their digital education and information culture. In today’s “Information Age,” this approach not only enhances students’ computer literacy but also expands their opportunities to work with software tools in studying specific physical phenomena. Knowledge, skills, and competencies acquired in physics through the use of software tools significantly contribute to the creation of websites at various levels, engagement in scientific research institutions, professional orientation, and a comprehensive understanding of physical processes that cannot be directly observed.

Literature Review

Numerous studies indicate that programming contributes to the development of planning and organizational skills, mathematical abilities, and abstract thinking. According to researchers, programming also fosters such competencies in students as problem-solving, critical thinking, creative thinking, algorithmic thinking, reflective thinking, teamwork, and learning-to-learn skills. It is evident that all of these competencies are essential for individuals living in the twenty-first century.

The thinking patterns and lifestyles of modern children are strongly influenced by computers. Policymakers supported by the technology industry increasingly demand that children be taught how technology works and that a “digital society” be prepared for an increasingly IT-driven global economy [2].

Pedagogical software tools are didactic resources designed to partially or fully automate the teaching and learning process through the use of computer technologies. The structure of pedagogical software tools includes programs (or sets of programs) aimed at achieving specific didactic objectives in teaching a particular subject, a set of technical and methodological documentation, and, when necessary, additional auxiliary resources.

Research Methods

Pedagogical software tools based on elements of students’ learning activities can be classified as follows. One group consists of tools directly used by students, while the other group includes tools employed by teachers in the course of working with students [3].

The first group includes:

- modeling and research software;
- computer-based training simulators;
- computer-based assessment programs;
- information and reference systems.

The second group includes:

- modeling and demonstration software;
- programs for generating and verifying individualized assignments.

Modeling research and demonstration software simulate the functioning of various physical, biological, ecological, economic, and other systems through mathematical models. Such models contain a set of input variables and parameters that allow variations in system behavior and enable the study of the laws and principles governing its operation. The difference between research-oriented and demonstration-oriented models lies in their didactic purpose. In

demonstration activities, the primary didactic factor is the visualization and presentation of a process or phenomenon, whereas research-oriented software should be constructed according to the principles of an operational system in which students independently identify subjectively new knowledge through exploration.

During practice activities, students work under software control while independently selecting learning strategies. Similarly, the pace of learning, the volume and complexity of tasks, and the level of assistance provided are individualized.

Computer-based assessment programs are designed to monitor students' knowledge and skills at all stages of instruction. Computer-based assessment should include:

- generating tasks according to sequences defined by the teacher (or selecting them from an existing database) and presenting them to students;
- providing students with tools for task completion (on-screen calculators, text editors, interfaces for entering answers, etc.);
- qualitatively evaluating task performance and analyzing errors during formative assessment;
- statistically processing the results of group assessments.

In addition, assessment programs, like training simulators, should ensure maximum adaptability to students' individual characteristics and capabilities. For this purpose, they should include adjustable parameters accessible to teachers. The absence of such parameters (so-called "rigid" programs) limits the effective use of pedagogical software tools to some extent.

Information and reference systems integrate programs and platforms used by students as sources of factual information. These include multimedia systems and global computer networks, primarily the Internet. After receiving an assignment from the teacher, students search for the necessary information within the system and assimilate it. Naturally, such activities require that students be prepared to independently search for information and process the data obtained.

Programs for generating and verifying individualized assignments are aimed at personalizing problem-solving practice by reducing repetition and varying tasks within a single topic from school problem collections. According to the method of creating individualized tasks, such programs are classified into banks, variators, and generators. These tools are used by teachers, after which assignments may be provided to students in a non-digital (paper-based) format, similar to collections of varied tasks in computer science. Subsequent assessment may be conducted by the teacher with or without the use of computers. In addition, a wide range of instructional videos and programming guides available on the Internet can be creatively utilized to develop students' creative abilities through teaching with pedagogical software tools [4].

Description of an Electromagnetic Accelerator Device. To enable students to apply theoretical knowledge in practice and master programming skills as described above, a description of an *electromagnetic accelerator* device is presented.

The electromagnetic accelerator operates based on the laws of electromagnetic induction and the interaction between magnetic fields and matter. The primary function of the device is to convert electrical energy into strong magnetic field energy within a short period of time and to demonstrate the process by which this field exerts a mechanical effect on a ferromagnetic core.

1. **Conservation and storage of electrical energy.** At the initial stage of the device operation, the energy obtained from the power source is accumulated in capacitors. In the capacitors, energy is stored in the form of an electric field, and its amount is determined by the classical expression:

$$E = \frac{1}{2}CU^2$$

where:

C – capacitance of the capacitor,

U – voltage.

This stage makes it possible to store energy in a stable state and subsequently transfer it within a very short time interval.

2. Formation of a current impulse. When the capacitor circuit is connected to an electromagnetic coil (solenoid), the energy stored in the capacitor is converted within a short time into a strong current impulse flowing through the coil. This process is time-limited and is characterized by a rapid increase and decrease of the current. With the appearance of the current impulse, the coil exhibits inductive properties. A self-induction voltage directed against the change in current arises, which electromagnetically balances the process.

3. Formation of a magnetic field. When current flows through the coil, a magnetic field is formed around it. The magnetic induction inside the solenoid can be approximately expressed by the following relationship:

$$B \sim \mu n I$$

where:

μ – magnetic permeability of the medium,

n – number of turns of the coil per unit length,

I – current strength.

The maximum value of the magnetic field is formed in the region close to the center of the solenoid, which causes spatial nonuniformity of the force acting on the ferromagnetic core

4. Force acting on the ferromagnetic core. The ferromagnetic core placed inside the solenoid becomes magnetized under the influence of the magnetic field. Due to the presence of a magnetic field gradient, an attractive force directed toward the region of higher field strength acts on the core. The nature of this force is explained by the tendency of the magnetic energy to reach a minimum. As a result, the core moves toward the center of the solenoid. This process clearly demonstrates the conversion of electrical energy into magnetic energy and then into mechanical energy.

5. Termination of the impulse and limitation of motion. When the current impulse ends, the magnetic field rapidly decays. The core continues its motion for a short time due to inertia; however, in the demonstration device it is retained by a mechanical constraint (captive mechanism). Therefore, the core does not exit into the external environment, and the device performs only a visual and scientific demonstration function.

6. Energy dissipation and return of the system to equilibrium. After the magnetic field disappears, the excess energy in the system is dissipated in the form of heat. Reverse voltages arising in inductive elements are suppressed through special protection circuits. After that, the device returns to its initial equilibrium state and becomes ready for the next experiment. This demonstration electromagnetic accelerator device clearly and safely illustrates electromagnetic induction, the magnetic field gradient, and the processes of energy conversion from one form to another. The device serves as a convenient model for studying the practical manifestations of electromagnetic phenomena for scientific and educational purposes.

In practice, this principle is widely applied in many processes, for example, in the construction industry for driving support piles to reinforce building foundations, in stone quarries

for moving and breaking rocks, as well as for driving various protective piles and similar applications (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Pile driving process in practice

Research results. Based on students’ knowledge gained from studying physics, particularly the “Magnetic Field” section [5], we recommend the following project to enhance understanding of physical processes, stimulate the development of innovative ideas, encourage inventions, and foster interest in programming these processes.

SAFE “CAPTIVE SOLENOID DEMO” FOR COMPLETE, DEMONSTRATION-LEVEL PROJECT

1. System operation algorithm

Buttons	The task is
BTN1 (ARM)	Charges capacitors up to 24 V
BTN2 (FIRE)	To the solenoid short impulse gives (100–200 ms)
Arduino	Limits time, ensures safety

2. A social electrical parameters (safe)

- 1) Voltage : 24 V DC
- 2) Maximum pulse time: ≤ 200 ms
- 3) energy : low (for demo)
- 4) root : captive (out (not going)

3. Necessary components (clear name and parameters)

Electronic components

Power and energy

Name	P arameters
DC Power Supply	24 V, 5 A
Capacitor C1	4700 μ F, 35 V, Low-ESR
Capacitor C2	100 nF, 50 V (for noise)
Discharge resistor R1	10 k Ω , 2 W

Solenoid and switch

Name	P arameters
Solenoid	24 V DC, 2–3 A, captive type , transparent

MOSFET	IRLZ44N (logic level)
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Protection

Name	Parameters
Flyback diode	1N5408 (3A)
TVS diode	SMBJ33A
Insurance	5 A automotive fuse

Management

Name	Parameters
Arduino	Arduino UNO or NANO
Button BTN1	NO Push Button
Button BTN2	NO Push Button
Button resistors	10 kΩ pull-down

Mechanical parts

- 1) s is light captive solenoid tube
- 2) front and back steel stop plates
- 3) core way along rubber shock absorber
- 4) protected (insulated) housing

4. Connection diagrammatic scheme - picture)

Flyback diode 1N5408:
 Cathode → +24V
 Anode → Solenoid drain tomoni

Arduino:
 D8 → Gate (100Ω orqali)
 BTN1 → D2 (ARM)
 BTN2 → D3 (FIRE)

GND → umumiy GND

5. Arduino kodi (xavfsiz cheklov bilan)

```
#define ARM_BTN 2
#define FIRE_BTN 3
#define SOLENOID_PIN 8
#define FIRE_TIME 150 // ms (xavfsiz impuls)
bool armed = false;
void setup() {
  pinMode(ARM_BTN, INPUT_PULLUP);
  pinMode(FIRE_BTN, INPUT_PULLUP);
  pinMode(SOLENOID_PIN, OUTPUT);
  digitalWrite(SOLENOID_PIN, LOW);
}
void loop() {
  // ARM tugmasi
  if (digitalRead(ARM_BTN) == LOW) {
    armed = true;
    delay(300); // debounce
  }
  // FIRE tugmasi
  if (armed && digitalRead(FIRE_BTN) == LOW) {
    digitalWrite(SOLENOID_PIN, HIGH);
    delay(FIRE_TIME);
    digitalWrite(SOLENOID_PIN, LOW);
    armed = false; // qayta arm qilish majburiy
    delay(500);
  }
}
```

6. Important Safety Notes

1. Do not open the solenoid.
2. The core must never move freely.
3. Do not touch the capacitor.
4. Wait 10–15 seconds after operation (R1 discharges the capacitor).

Conclusion

When carrying out such projects, it is emphasized that strict compliance with technical safety rules is mandatory, and before starting work, students must consult with the teacher or a qualified specialist.

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